

*Effect of Ampicillin Sodium on the Pattern of Nephrotoxicity in Laboratory Albino Rat, *Rattus norvegicus**

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Running title: *Nephrotoxicity by ampicillin sodium*

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Abstract

Ampicillin sodium was investigated for nephrotoxicity if any in the rat at a dose (40 mg/kg b.w.) lower than the medically prescribed one. Ampicillin caused an increase in acid and alkaline phosphatase activity, creatinine, blood urea nitrogen in both urine and serum of treated rats compared to control and saline-treated rats that indicated impairment of glomerular functions. Increased TBARS level and decreased total antioxidative status, SOD and GSH activity following ampicillin injection indicated increased ROS and oxidative destruction in the kidney compared to control and saline-treated rats. Decreased total kidney cortical protein following ampicillin injection indicating the extent of degradation of the membrane lipids. The histological observation of decreased capsular space of the Bowman's cup and luminal space of proximal convoluted tubule received support from the biochemical observation. This study on laboratory rats suggest that nephrotoxicity by ampicillin sodium can be assessed at a dose below the recommended /prescribed for treatment.

Keywords: Ampicillin sodium, kidney, nephrotoxicity, oxidative stress, *Rattus norvegicus*.

Introduction

It has been reported that the toxic effect of widely used drugs is the influence of an oxidative reaction that takes place in the secretory function of excretion attracting macrophages and neutrophil granulocytes in glomerular vesicular epithelial cells (GVEC), basolateral membrane, and proximal convoluted tubule (PCT) of the kidney. These stimulated neutrophils and macrophages are subjected to oxidative stress *via* numerous moderator proteins at the renal level, reflected in blood biochemistry and renal filtrates. Antibiotics are known to be one of the important causes of drug-induced nephrotoxicity [1]. Most antibiotics are nephrotoxic since a minor but substantial proportion of the administered dose (<5%) is engaged in the epithelial cells lining, S1 and S2 segments of the kidney's proximal tubules [2]. Antibiotics accrued by these cells are primarily restricted with endosomal and lysosomal vacuoles [3, 4] but are also localized with the Golgi complex [3]. They provoke a range of morphological and functional variations of cumulative sternness, aminoglycosides induce noticeable and distinctive changes in lysosomes of proximal tubular cells reliable with the accumulation of polar lipids (myeloid bodies) [5-7]. These changes are preceded and accompanied by signs of tubular dysfunctions or alterations by the release of brush border and lysosomal enzymes; decreased reabsorption of filtered proteins; wasting of K⁺, Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺, and glucose; phospholipiduria; and cast excretion

[8]. Ototoxicity is the second main adverse effect of antibiotics in contrast to nephrotoxicity, which is irreversible [9].

Ampicillin, a β -lactam, a broad-spectrum antibiotic used against gram -ve bacterium is very often used in intra-renal infections. Nephrotoxicity caused by Ampicillin has never been reported, except Deb et al [10] who compared tetracycline and ampicillin for its renal toxicity. When acute doses of ampicillin (1000mg/kg body wt.) are given for several days in severe infections like meningitis, the patient develops crystalluria. A case report suggests oligourea and intratubular obstructive renal failure. It has been found that the intra-renal distribution of ampicillin in normal rats [11] and non-diseased human kidneys [12] shows a moderate gradient of concentration between serum, cortex, and medulla [11]. But no report exists which could explain the basic mechanism by which ampicillin causes renal toxicity. The dose we have used in this study is 40 mg/kg body weight, which is lower than that prescribed for general infections (50 mg/kg body weight). Therefore, the present study reports nephrotoxicity by ampicillin sodium in rats and highlighted the possible factors responsible for renal toxicity in a laboratory animal *Rattus norvegicus*.

Materials and Methods

Twenty-one adult male rats (150g to 200g each) from the in-bred colonies of animal house, Dept. Zoology were used in this study and acclimatized for three days in a room fully exposed to ambient conditions (Light 12.50 h; Temp. 20–25°C; Humidity, 29–50%). The rats were housed in polypropylene commercial cages (25" X 75" X 30") and had access to commercial food and water *ad libitum*. Later, the rats were divided into three groups (n=7 in each group).

All the experiments were conducted in accordance with the institutional practice and within the framework of revised animal act (scientific procedure), CPCSEA of Govt. of India.

Group I: Control

Seven male rats were kept in natural environmental conditions (NDL; 12hrs. and 42 min light; June) as mentioned above without any treatment but handled every day.

Group II: Saline treated

Seven male rats were kept in natural environmental conditions (NDL) as mentioned above. A single intraperitoneal dose of 0.1% ml 0.9% NaCl saline (1ml/kg body wt./ day solution prepared in triple-distilled water) was given for seven days.

Group III: Ampicillin treatment:

Ampicillin sodium I.P. (equivalent to Anhydrous Ampicillin I.P.) of 500mg vials for injection was purchased as BIOCILIN® (manufactured by BIOCHEM Pharmaceutical Industries Ltd. Mumbai INDIA). The powder was reconstituted in sterile triple distilled water supplied with and then was diluted further to make 40mg/ml concentration. Thus rats received finally 40mg/kg body weight/day i.e. 0.1 ml of the final concentration for seven days.

Sample collection:

All the treatments were given for seven days and on the eighth day, (after 24 hours of last treatments) rats were sacrificed (decapitated) under deep either anesthesia. The bladder was surgically removed and emptied by supra-pubic puncture. This procedure ensured the collection of urine for 60 min. At the time of sacrifice, thus urine was collected, and its volume was measured and biochemical indices such as blood urea nitrogen (BUN), acid phosphatase (ACP), alkaline phosphatase (ALP), creatinine, and urea were estimated. After a midline abdominal incision, both kidneys were removed and uncovered from their capsule, weighed, and slit by longitudinal incision. Cortical, medullary (outer medulla), and papillary (inner medulla-papillary tip) components were collected under a dissecting microscope and were verified under a light microscope. Renal cortical tissue homogenates (10%) were made

separately in 20 mM Tris-HCl buffer (pH 7.4) for the detection of superoxide dismutase activity (SOD), lipid peroxidation level (TBARS), and total antioxidative status (TAS %). Trunk blood was collected in separate centrifuge tubes for biochemical estimations that are BUN, ACP, ALP, creatinine, and total blood protein. Kidney tissues were also fixed in Bouin's fluid for histological studies.

Lipid Peroxidation assay by (TBARS) level estimation:

Kidney cortical region was excised and weighed for the preparation of 10% tissue homogenates in 20 mM Tris Hydrochloride (HCl) buffer (pH 7.4) (SRL, Mumbai, India). The homogenates were centrifuged at 3000 g for 15 min at 4°C and supernatant was subjected to thiobarbituric acid (TBA) (SRL, Mumbai, India) assay by mixing it with 8.1% SDS, 20% acetic acid, 0.8% TBA, and boiling for 1 h at 95°C. The reaction mixture was cooled without delay in running water and robustly shaken with n-butanol and pyridine reagent (15:1) and centrifuged for 10 min at 1500 g [13]. The absorbance of the top phase was measured at 534 nm. LPO was expressed as TBARS in nmol/g tissue wt., by taking 1, 1, 3, 3-tetra ethoxy propane (TEP) (SRL, Mumbai, India) as standard. The standard curve was calibrated using a 10 nM concentration of TEP.

Superoxide dismutase assay (SOD)

Homogenates (10%) of all kidney cortical tissues were prepared in 150 mM phosphate-buffered saline (PBS, pH 7.4) and centrifuged at 12000 g for 30 min at 4°C. The supernatant was centrifuged another time at 12000 g for 60 min at 4°C and then processed for enzymatic activity based on the modified spectrophotometric method using nitrite formation by superoxide radicals [14]. 0.5 ml of homogenate was added to 1.4 ml of a reaction mixture comprising of 50 mM phosphate buffer (pH 7.4), 20 mM L-Methionine, 1% (v/v) Triton X-100, 10 mM hydroxylamine hydrochloride, 50 µM ethylene diamine tetra-acetic acid (EDTA) (SRL, Mumbai, India) followed by a brief pre-incubation at 37°C for 5 min. Later, 0.8 ml of riboflavin was added to all samples along with control containing buffer instead of sample and then exposed to two 20 W fluorescent lamps fitted parallel to each other in an aluminum foil coated wooden box. After 10 min of exposure, 1 ml of freshly prepared Greiss reagent (1% sulphanilamide, 5% orthophosphoric acid, 0.1% N-1-naphthylethyl enediamine dihydrochloride) (SRL, Mumbai, India) was added, and absorbance of the color formed was deliberated at 543 nm. One unit of enzyme activity is defined as the amount of SOD inhibiting 50% of nitrite formation under assay conditions.

Total antioxidative status (TAS %)

The total antioxidative status of kidney cortical tissue was evaluated by ABTS (2, 2'-azino-bis (3-ethylbenzthiazoline-6-sulphonic acid) (SRL, Mumbai, India) assay following the method of Rice-Evans and Miller [15] with slight modifications. A stock solution of ABTS radical cations was prepared one day before the assay by mixing 5 ml of 7 mM ABTS with 1 ml of 14.7 mM potassium persulfate and kept in dark at room temperature for 16 h. The stock solution of ABTS radical cations was then diluted with distilled water till its absorbance reached 0.7 at 734 nm. ABTS radical cation was generated by oxidation of ABTS with potassium persulfate. 2.95 ml of ABTS radical cation solution were mixed with 50 µl of 10% tissue homogenate and the decrease in absorbance was monitored for 60 min at 6 min intervals at 734 nm.

The activity was compared with the original (ABTS^{•+}) solution using ascorbic acid as standard. Suitable solvent blanks were run in each assay. Each experiment was carried out in triplicate. The total antioxidant capacity (TAs %) was expressed as percent inhibition of the bleaching concerning aqueous control following the equation:

$$\text{Inhibition of A734 (\%)} = (1 - A_f/A_o) \times 100$$

A₀= absorbance of uninhibited radical cation.

A_f= absorbance measured 6 minutes after the addition of the test sample.

Biochemical estimations in blood and urine

Concentrations of creatinine, urea nitrogen, urea in plasma, and urine, in addition to the activity of alkaline phosphatase, acid phosphatase were measured by using kits supplied by the manufacturer (Span Diagnostics Ltd. Mumbai, India). All chemical analyses were performed in plasma, urine, or renal homogenates after appropriate calibration of the instruments with standard GSH concentration was estimated spectrophotometrically with Ellman's method modified by Sedalk and Lindsay [16].

Total kidney cortical protein content

Total kidney cortical protein content in tissue homogenate was determined following the method of Lowry et al., [17] and presented as mg/g tissue weight.

Histology

After fixation in Bouin's fluid for 22 hours, the kidney was paraffin-embedded and slashed into 6- μ m sections. Deparaffinized sections were stained using hematoxylin and eosin. Kidney morphology was observed under a microscope (Leica MPV-3, Germany) and documented. The morphometric analysis of capsular space and cellular integrity (PCT, DCT & glomerulus) of kidney cortical region were done in 20 serial sections randomly chosen from each animal with the help of filar ocular micrometer (Webcon Pvt. Ltd. Varanasi, India)

Statistical analysis

All the data were expressed as means \pm SEM of at least five animals per group. Data comparisons were statistically analyzed by using ANOVA followed by Student Newman-Keuls' multiple range tests. The differences were considered statistically significant when $p < 0.05$ [18].

Results

Biochemical estimation of ACP, ALP, Creatinine, and Urea in blood and urine showed a significant ($p < 0.01$) increase in groups treated with ampicillin sodium compared to controls, saline, and vehicle-treated ones (Plate 1&2). There was a slight decrease in blood ACP and Urea in groups treated with saline which was not significant. An increase in TBARS level of Ampicillin treated groups was highly significant ($p < 0.01$) while total antioxidative capacity (TAS %) and total blood proteins decreased noticeably ($p < 0.01$) when compared to all other groups (Plate 3).

An increase in superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity in saline and vehicle-treated groups was non-significant but their activity decreased significantly ($p < 0.01$) in ampicillin treated groups (Plate 3).

Plate. 1
 Effect of ampicillin and saline treatment on (A) ACP in blood (B) ACP in urine (C) ALK in Urine (D) ALK in Blood to access nephrotoxicity in rats, (N=7). Histogram represent Mean \pm SEM, Vertical bar on each histogram represent standard error of mean, * $p < 0.05$ and ** $p < 0.01$. ACP and ALK of ampicillin treated group was compared to control and saline treated groups.

Plate. 2
 Effect of ampicillin and saline treatment on Blood Urea (A) Urine Urea (B) and creatinine in Urine (C) and Blood (D) to access nephrotoxicity in rats, (N=7). Histogram represent Mean \pm SEM, Vertical bar on each histogram represent standard error of mean, * $p < 0.05$ and ** $p < 0.01$. Urea and creatinine of ampicillin treated group was compared to control and saline treated groups.

Plate 3:
 (A) Effect of ampicillin and saline on super oxide-dismutase activity (SOD) to assess free radical load in rats (N=7). Histogram represent Mean \pm SEM, Vertical bar on each histogram represent standard error of mean, * p<0.05 and ** p<0.01. SOD in kidney cortical tissues homogenates of ampicillin treated group was compared to control and saline treated groups.
 (B) Effect of ampicillin and saline on the total antioxidant status (TAS) to assess free radical load in rats (N=7). Histogram represent Mean \pm SEM, Vertical bar on each histogram represent standard error of mean, * p<0.05 and ** p<0.01. TAS in kidney cortical tissues homogenates of ampicillin treated group was compared to control and saline treated groups.
 (C) Effect of ampicillin and saline on the TBARS level to assess the extent of protein degradation in rats (N=7). Histogram represent Mean \pm SEM, Vertical bar on each histogram represent standard error of mean, * p<0.05 and ** p<0.01. TBARS in kidney cortical tissues homogenates of ampicillin treated group was compared to control and saline treated groups.
 (D) Effect of ampicillin and saline on the total plasma protein to assess nephrotoxicity in rats (N=7). Histogram represent Mean \pm SEM, Vertical bar on each histogram represent standard error of mean, * p<0.05 and ** p<0.01. Total plasma protein of ampicillin treated group was compared to control and saline treated groups.

Morphometric Analysis (Table 1) and Histological observation (Plate 4) showed significant (p<0.01) decrease in capsular space of Bowman’s capsule ($2.21 \pm 0.14\mu\text{m}$) and luminal space of PCT ($06.21 \pm 1.14 \mu\text{m}$) in Ampicillin treated groups when compared with the groups treated with saline and control.

MEASUREMENT OF CAPSULAR SPACE (CS) OF BOWMAN'S CAPSULE AND LUMINAL SPACE OF PCT (20 SECTIONS/GROUP)

Treatments	Capsular Space (CS) of Bowman's cup	Luminal space of PCT
Control	$7.21 \pm 0.24 \mu\text{m}$	$13.21 \pm 1.14 \mu\text{m}$
Saline (1 ml/ animal i.v in morning hours 11-12 am)	$7.01 \pm 0.23 \mu\text{m}$	$12.11 \pm 1.14 \mu\text{m}$
Ampicillin sodium (40mg/Eg body wt. i.v in morning hours 11-12 am)	$2.21 \pm 0.14^{**} \mu\text{m}$	$06.21 \pm 1.14^{**} \mu\text{m}$

Morphometric analysis showing changes in the capillary diameter of capsular space (CS) of Bowman's cup, luminal space of proximal convoluted tubule in control, saline and ampicillin treated groups. Mean \pm SEM; Significance of difference **p<0.01, Control vs saline and ampicillin treated groups.

Plate. 4
Histomicrograph of rat kidney cortical region showing glomerulus (G), capsular space (CS), Brush bordered vesicular epithelial cells (BBVEC) (*) proximal convoluted tubule (PCT), distal convoluted tubule (DCT), loop of henele and collecting tubule. (Under 40X objective) A-control, B-saline treated and C- ampicillin treated.

Discussion

The main restriction of the clinical use of antibiotic drugs persists to be an apprehension for the development of hepatotoxicity and nephrotoxicity. Evidence from investigations with animals and humans have confirmed a relationship between the nephrotoxic effects of antibiotic drugs and the accrual of these antibiotic drugs in the cortical region of the kidney [6, 19]. Proximal renal tubular epithelial (PRTE) cells, glomerular basement membrane (GBM) cells, and glomerular vesicular epithelial (GVE) cells are thought to be the site of antibiotic nephrotoxicity. Researchers have pointed out that inhibition of phosphatidylinositol phospholipases A1 and A2 by aminoglycosides leads to the formation of lamellar bodies which are postulated to lead to cellular toxicity [20]. They are not metabolized in the body but are basically removed by glomerular filtration and partially reabsorbed by proximal convoluted tubular cells. Lysosomes are known to be the unique site of accrual of antibiotics into proximal tubular cells [21, 22]. They stimulate lysosomal phospholipidosis [23] which is associated with cellular necrosis and post-necrotic cell degeneration [24].

Nephrotoxicity caused by Ampicillin has never been reported, except Deb et al [10] who compared tetracycline and ampicillin for its renal toxicity. When acute doses of ampicillin (1000mg/kg body wt.) are given for several days in severe infections like meningitis, the patient develops crystalluria. Our data suggest that nephrotoxicity was observed following

ampicillin treatment at a concentration of 40mg/kg body wt. which was lower than the one used clinically (50mg/kg body wt.). We evaluated the nephrotoxicity by monitoring the i) concentration of serum creatinine and urea nitrogen (BUN) ii) levels of the intracellular enzymes namely, superoxide dismutase (SOD), iii) concentration of cellular metabolic intermediates like reduced glutathione (GSH), total kidney cortical protein, iv) the level of lipid peroxidation, TBARS level, total antioxidant status (%TAS) in the kidney tissue homogenates of the treated animals.

As it is well known that creatinine, ACP, ALP, and BUN is an imperative measure of renal function. A noteworthy decline in their levels of blood and urine was recorded after ampicillin treatment suggesting an impairment of glomerular functions and cellular alteration as inferred by histological observations as well. The morphometric analysis further showed impaired renal structure i.e. increased capsular and renal space following ampicillin treatment. Increased level of alkaline phosphatase, acid phosphatase, creatinine, and urea in urine as well as in blood following Ampicillin treatment indicates the direct toxic effects of Ampicillin on the above parameters when compared to the control group. Reactive oxygen species and other free radicals are considered important mediators of renal cell injury by toxic reactions and renal ischemia [25, 26]. The synthesis of lipid-free radicals and lipid peroxide is deemed as an important feature of cell injury. The abundance of free radicals could lead to uncontrolled chain reactions and lipid peroxidation. The enhanced levels of lipid peroxidation (TBARS) in the present study reveal ampicillin provoked lipid peroxidation in the kidney via free radicals. A significant surge in TBARS and alterations in activities of SOD, catalase, and GPx are indicative of UN induced oxidative balance perturbation [27] Enzymes, such as ACP and ALP, are located in the brush border of the proximal tubule epithelium. The increase of the concentration of these enzymes in the urine denotes lesions in the brush border membrane and structural alterations due to loss of the microvillus, which reduces the reabsorption of proteins filtered [28]. Lipid peroxidation status was found to be significantly elevated in ampicillin treated groups when compared to controls. The reason for such effects could be due to the oxidative stress i. e. free radical load induced by Ampicillin metabolism. The total antioxidative status decreased following the Ampicillin treatment may be due to high free radical generation by Ampicillin toxicity (metabolism).

Ampicillin treatment reduced the SOD activity below the control levels indicating the presence/involvement of fewer superoxide radicals, which also indicates that the ampicillin toxicity is not mediated or caused by SOD radicals. It could be that Hydroxyl radicals (OH) are being affected by Ampicillin and it will be the next target of the study. The result indicates that Ampicillin is causing nephrotoxicity by inducing free radical load probably other than superoxide (SOD) radicals. Since the results are of high clinical value further dose-dependent studies were accomplished. Several experimental details are indicating that nephrotoxic drugs may also alter the concentrations of MDA, GSH, BUN [29, 30] which are generally applied to observe the progress and degree of renal tubular injury owing to oxidative stress. Similarly, we as well found a high level of BUN, urea, and GSH in ampicillin treated rats which further prove nephrotoxicity caused by ampicillin. It has also been documented that the light and electron microscopic evaluation were more susceptible than the other methods in determining toxicity [31]. The concentrated accumulation of Ampicillin in the proximal tubule cells would be associated with nephrotoxicity by other drugs as observed in histological observation by our group and others [32].

In conclusion, the present study provides evidences that ampicillin can cause nephrotoxicity even at a lower dose than the clinically recommended one. Therefore, it

becomes necessary to take preventive measures against its use to control the generation of free radicals in the renal system which might lead to nephrotoxicity due to local oxidative stress.

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Declarations of interest

No conflict of interest could be perceived as; (a) prejudicing the impartiality of the research reported, or (b) fully declares any financial or other potential conflicts of interest.

Ethical clearance

All the experiments on animals were conducted in accordance with the institutional practices within the framework of the revised animal (Scientific Procedures) Act of 2002 of the Government of India on Animal welfare.

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